

WRESTLING TYPES B MENTAL TRAINER CHARACTERISTICS OF PROFESSIONAL TRAINING

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Abstract. *The article analyzed the features of the professional training of a specialist who implements the educational-coaching process in oriental martial arts. The general and special requirements for the trainer have been disclosed. It was noted that the three-step model of the specialist's professional training includes physical, psychological-pedagogical and special theoretical training.*

Key words: *eastern martial arts, educational and training process, personal and professional requirements, types of training, three-level training.*

БОРЬБА ВИДОВ Б МЕНТАЛЬНЫЙ ТРЕНЕР ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ

Аннотация. *В статье проанализированы особенности профессиональной подготовки специалиста, реализующего учебно-тренировочный процесс в восточных единоборствах. Раскрыты общие и специальные требования к тренеру. Отмечено, что трехступенчатая модель профессиональной подготовки специалиста включает физическую, психолого-педагогическую и специально-теоретическую подготовку.*

Ключевые слова: *восточные единоборства, учебно-тренировочный процесс, лично-профессиональные требования, виды обучения, трехступенчатая подготовка.*

INTRODUCTION

Building a morally and physically healthy, knowledge-enriched society in Uzbekistan puts modernization tasks before the educational system. To solve these tasks, it is necessary to improve the quality of general education and professional training of physical culture and sports specialists based on the use of training methods. Mastering the elements of modern combat techniques and being able to use them remains one of the main components of training specialists in the field of physical education and sports. This requires that physical culture faculties, universities and institutes introduce, develop and implement career-oriented software-pedagogical tools and courses on combat training in the educational process. They will be directed to acquire the basics of necessary knowledge, use them in professional-pedagogical activities, and gather personal experience. Training of specialists in Eastern martial arts is a new direction in the social culture education system. Treating Eastern martial arts as one of the directions of modern physical culture and sports allows us to expand the scope of their educational opportunities and use them as an effective system of personal self-development, which includes the aspiration to realize the physical, spiritual and moral potential of a person.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

The feature of Eastern martial arts is that people of all ages can be involved in the training. It is noted that people from 5 to 60 years old, and even older, participate in classes in karate, taekwondo, aikido, judo, wushu. Due to the expansion of the range of tasks solved by health-giving, sports, practical and other means of physical education, the need to train specialists of various levels has arisen. They should be able to carry out the educational and training process with people of different ages, because oriental martial arts can be practiced in

kindergarten, sports school, private school, educational institutions. A specialist in oriental martial arts should have the necessary qualities and skills for pedagogical and coaching activities. need The general pedagogical requirements for a trainer are a high level of moral self-awareness, pedagogical education, a broad ideological and political outlook, stable willpower, knowledge of pedagogy, psychology and biology, a high general cultural level, organizational skills, team management skills, reputation among students. consists of such things as winning. Special students who will be engaged in coaching activities: know the theoretical and methodical bases of physical training, medical supervision; to acquire technical and tactical skills; to know achievements in sports; ability to select students who are capable of this type of sport; being able to draw up a prospective training plan, taking into account their individual characteristics when training athletes; to educate students' desire to constantly engage in sports; to have the skills to prepare athletes to achieve high results in competitions.

RESEARCH RESULTS NAD DISCUSSION

It should be noted that a trainer is a creative person. For his effective work, attention, intelligence, intuition, imagination, foresight, avoidance of templates, originality, initiative, high organization and work ability are necessary. Today, the capabilities of hand-to-hand combat techniques have moved far beyond the practice of using them in the training process. If a certain experience is gained in the study of certain subjects (economics, physics-mathematics, technology and informatics), the use of modern martial arts achievements in physical culture classes seems to be much less or not used at all. Therefore, today, actively changing the content and tools of health-giving physical culture, revising the methodology of passing physical culture classes and the requirements for it, developing the methodical system of professional pedagogical training of students of physical culture faculties based on the integration of health-giving and modern combat technologies are among the problems awaiting their solution. The three-step model of the professional training of a specialist in oriental martial arts, developed by MIStankin, allows to solve this problem to a certain extent. The first step is the foundation of the activity, its basis, base. In order to master the technique of the chosen type of martial arts, first of all, it is necessary to have sufficient physical preparation (condition). Students cannot be taught without a sufficient amount of technique. The volume of technical actions is reflected by sports qualification (qualification). By improving his sports skills, an expert improves his movement preparation both quantitatively and qualitatively. Therefore, preparation of movement is the basis of the model of an expert in oriental martial arts. The second step is psychological and pedagogical preparation. The profession of a teacher requires the presence of pedagogical skills and important professional qualities, which are necessary to transfer the experience of movement (to teach the technique of the chosen martial art and to improve the level of physical condition) to the learners. The third level reflects special theoretical training. In order to become an expert, it is necessary to have the ability to master and teach techniques, but also to know where and how to use them. A trainer with special knowledge can manage the training process, organize it in accordance with the goals and tasks, and find ways to solve the problems that have arisen by researching the influence of various factors on the results of the trainees.

CONCLUSION

As a result of such an approach to the system of modern physical culture education, it will be possible to determine the necessary level of knowledge and, accordingly, the level of competence of the future teacher, so that the teacher can determine the tasks before him.

implements the scope of his practical activities. The training of a specialist in oriental martial arts should represent a system that covers the entire process, from the moment of determining the specialty of the future applicant to entering a higher educational institution and passing the next stage of higher education.

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